

Eurodoc Statement on Doctoral Supervision

Vision of the doctoral supervision statement

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) envisions a future where doctoral supervision acts as a catalyst that empowers early career researchers to become the next generation of experts and leaders who conduct research, drive innovation towards positive societal change, and address the global challenges of today and tomorrow. We champion a model of doctoral supervision that nurtures well-rounded scholars, so they can make impactful contributions and expand human knowledge through an environment of creativity, critical thinking, and collaboration. Ultimately, the resilience of the research and higher education sector lies in our diversity of thought and experience – this is our strength.

Introduction

The relationship between the doctoral candidate and the doctoral supervisors is at the heart of doctoral education. An open and constructive candidate-supervisor relationship is necessary for high-quality doctoral education, enhancing the candidate's research and professional development both during and after their doctorate. Importantly, it is a relationship built on mutual trust and respect, which must adapt and balance different aspects of leadership over time.

In this document, we outline Eurodoc's position on supervision in doctoral education. The objective is to provide a view on the goals, prerequisites, and conditions of doctoral supervision from the perspective of doctoral candidates and early career researchers in the modern third-cycle education system in Europe. The document presents the goals of doctoral supervision, followed by an exploration of various aspects of the supervisory process: the candidate-supervisor relationship, the supervisory team, supervisor training, and the broader academic environment in which supervision takes place. It concludes with a few aspects of academic freedom specifically relevant to doctoral supervision. For a broader view on the purpose and objectives of doctoral education in general, please refer to Eurodoc's previous statement "The Doctoral Education – a Research Education".¹

The format of doctoral education differs greatly between, and partially also within, European countries. This plurality is both a strength and a challenge and has been chartered by Eurodoc in a previous project of the Working Group for Doctoral Training.² However, there are a number of generic components of doctoral supervision that exhibit important parallels across European countries and beyond.

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¹ Eurodoc, "The Doctoral Education – a Research Education", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277824>

² Eurodoc, "Doctorates across Europe", <https://eurodoc.net/doctoral-training-wg/doctorates-across-europe>

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Goals and components of doctoral supervision

Doctoral education is a research education.^{3,4} Thus, the central part of doctoral education is to perform research under supervision, with the ultimate goal of becoming an independent researcher working without supervision. Supervision is a critical component of doctoral education; it provides the necessary structure for the doctoral candidate to explore a research area while supporting the development of their skills, creativity, and intellectual autonomy. This guidance allows doctoral candidates to complete their research successfully and eventually become independent scholars. High-quality supervision is therefore not just at the heart of doctoral education, but of the research and higher education system as such.

The goal of doctoral supervision is to create opportunities for the doctoral candidates to identify and develop

- 1) skills and competencies that are generally necessary for academic work,
- 2) skills and competencies that are required formally for obtaining the doctoral degree,
- 3) skills and competencies that the doctoral candidate optionally wishes to obtain for reasons of scientific interest or career plans, which are also related to the field of doctoral education.

Since supervision needs to be based on and comply with existing rules, regulations, and recommendations, it benefits from structured approaches that support clarity and accountability. At the same time, supervision remains an academic craft, as it is developed through experience and personal commitment, while leaving room for personal style and judgement. It is fundamentally a relationship of mutual trust and confidence. The doctoral candidate must be able to trust the supervisors to provide adequate guidance to achieve the goals set out at the commencement of doctoral training within the timeframe of the doctoral education. Conversely, the supervisors must be able to trust the candidate's commitment to and responsibility for their research and academic development.

The supervising role is multifaceted as it combines the roles of mentor, manager, role model, facilitator, trustee, teacher, among others. Initially, the doctoral supervisors aid in creating a plan for the doctoral candidate's research and education that formulates a timeline as well as the methods, route, and target of the doctoral education and research. The continuous progress of the candidate is monitored with a system or plan that marks the completion of adaptable milestones. This not only helps the supervisor to keep track of the progress and the institution to

³ Eurodoc, "The Doctoral Education – a Research Education", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277824>

⁴ EUA, "Salzburg II recommendations", <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/615:salzburg-ii-%E2%80%93-recommendations.html>

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ensure a framework is in place, but also serves the candidate in regularly consolidating ideas and research goals.⁵

While institutions need to provide the training and overarching framework for research integrity, it is the supervisors' responsibility to ensure that the doctoral candidate follows the scientific code of conduct (e.g. ethics of science, data reliability, and open science), and to model and uphold these principles throughout the doctoral education process. Supervisors also stand as guarantors of the scientific integrity of the doctoral candidate's work until their graduation from doctoral education.

Furthermore, doctoral supervisors provide guidance on opportunities available to the doctoral candidate during and after their doctoral education, as well as introduce the doctoral candidate to both the local and international research environment (e.g., scientific societies, journals, conferences, or personal networks). Thus, good supervision achieves a balance between providing at times concrete advice and constructive feedback, and at times guiding the doctoral candidate more broadly in shaping both their doctoral education and future careers, whether inside or outside of academia.

Supervision, in other words, plays a core role in the successful completion of third cycle education, in the conditions under which the doctoral candidate is working during that period, and in ensuring that the doctoral candidate becomes a flourishing, independent academic. It is the institution, however, that awards the doctoral degree and is, thus, ultimately responsible for the quality of the education and the working environment of the doctoral candidate. This in turn means that there is a heightened institutional responsibility for ensuring the conditions and frameworks for high-quality supervision.

The candidate-supervisor relationship

The primary component of doctoral supervision is the relationship between the doctoral candidate and their supervisors, particularly their main supervisor, which plays a pivotal role in ensuring a successful research process. The effectiveness of doctoral supervision relies on collaboration, which underlines the importance of a strong relationship between the supervisor and the doctoral candidate. The institution has the responsibility to put frameworks for supervision in place to set the necessary parameters that ensure quality, adequacy, and transparency regarding the education and research guidance received by the doctoral candidate.⁶ The supervisors and the doctoral candidate in turn should discuss and agree on the

⁵ On the importance of such a plan for quality assurance and for ensuring the EHEA fundamental values, especially academic freedom, in the context of third cycle education, see Saugmann, P. M., Schoch, H. "Frameworks for Doctoral Education: Academic Freedom of Doctoral Candidates Across Europe" in *European Higher Education Area 2030: Bridging Realities for Tomorrow's Higher Education*, edited by A. Curaj, R. Pricopie, C. M. Hâj, Springer Nature, 2025.

⁶ The broader introduction of doctoral schools in Europe over the course of the last decade has, for example, been a vehicle through which the institutional frameworks and responsibility for doctoral education have been clarified, tightened, and streamlined.

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concrete form of supervision in writing or verbally. Preferably, this is in the form of a documented supervision agreement, which can adapt and change over time. The relationship between the candidate and supervisor is a mutual long-term commitment and, as such, must be built on clear mutual expectations.

The academic practice of supervision places a significant responsibility on the supervisor as it requires that they adapt their approach to each candidate's background, prior knowledge, experience, and motivation. Not losing sight of the balance between critical feedback and encouragement is equally key for allowing the candidate's curiosity and initiative to flourish. Thus, it is central that academic institutions make sure that supervisors are given access to and take part in sufficient training and that they are continuously encouraged to reflect on supervisory practices and ignite their passion for research, the pursuit of knowledge, and scholarship in the next generation of early-career researchers. Institutions must also ensure that supervisors are allocated sufficient working time for supervision within their formal workload, so that it is recognised as an essential part of academic responsibilities rather than treated as additional or invisible labour. To ensure accountability and the professional development of supervisors, institutions should also evaluate supervisory performance - integrating PhD candidates' feedback - as part of regular staff reviews, and consider ways to acknowledge and reward good supervision while addressing persistent shortcomings. To promote a healthy degree of independence, supervisors should not have the exclusive authority to terminate or fundamentally change the conditions of the doctoral candidate's work contract. This reduces power concentration in one individual and mitigates the risk of potential abuse.

Supervising team

Each doctoral candidate should have both a main supervisor and at least one co-supervisor. Having multiple individuals involved in the supervision team allows a distribution of roles according to individual competencies within that supervision setup and reduces the doctoral candidate's dependence on one single individual. It furthermore contributes to creating a sustainable workload for the supervisors and allows for the gradual introduction of more junior supervisors into the role. The doctoral candidate may meet at different frequencies with the various supervisors. These supervisors may also play different roles, e.g. cover different topics, be more influential at different stages, or provide guidance at different strategic or operational levels. The main supervisor is typically appointed at the start of the doctoral education and is the person with whom the doctoral candidate maintains the most continuous contact throughout the process. With time, the supervisor gains the necessary insight into the doctoral candidate's work and situation to identify needs and provide adequate guidance and support. As long as the relationship between the doctoral candidate and main supervisor works well, the doctoral candidate ideally has the same main supervisor throughout the entire doctoral education.

All supervisors involved thus make up the supervising team. While changes in the supervising team can occur over the course of doctoral education, these are ideally not so extensive as to disrupt the progression of the doctoral candidate. Depending on the project, it may also be

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pertinent to bring in supervisors with other competencies or experiences, either for the project development or for the career development of the doctoral candidate. In this way, postdoctoral researchers and domain experts can be involved in the supervising team. Involvement can either be formal or informal, but all contributions of co-supervisors must be formally recognised. Different supervisors should have different roles allocated depending on their previous experiences and career level.

Agreement of mutual expectations

During the start of this long-term trajectory of the doctoral candidate, it is important to make clear arrangements with the supervisors involved, for example in the form of a written supervision agreement. Topics to be addressed include meeting frequency and approximate duration, ways of collaboration and feedback, or conference, workshop, and course participation.⁷ Since different stages of doctoral education require different forms of supervision, the discussion on mutual expectations needs to be revisited regularly. The host institutions facilitate this, e.g. by providing a list of questions or requirements to be discussed by the candidate and supervisors.

The time allocated to supervision is critical for the progress of the doctoral candidate. However, how much time is needed depends on the context, the discipline, the form of supervision, as well as the individual preference of both the doctoral candidate and the supervisors. The form, time, and frequency of supervision is agreed upon in advance between the doctoral candidate and the supervisor and amended as needed throughout the course of doctoral training. A framework for establishing these expectations is provided by the institution or a suitable external stakeholder. The doctoral candidate must always have the right to change supervisors upon request.

Supervision is, however, a reciprocal relationship. The doctoral candidate can expect good supervision. Simultaneously, the supervisor can expect the candidate to grow and develop independence, initiative, and self-guidance, as appropriate based on their skills and competences, and their progress over the course of the doctoral education. Supervisors play a key role in nurturing these qualities, particularly in the early stages of the doctorate, by guiding, motivating and encouraging the candidate's academic growth and confidence. Since the candidate is supposed to fulfil certain research outputs and deliverables, the supervisor and the candidate share responsibilities towards their completion.

⁷ University of Leiden, "Golden rules for PhD supervision",
<https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/binaries/content/assets/ul2staff/onderzoek/promoveren/golden-rules-phd-supervision>

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Training of doctoral supervisors

Doctoral supervision is a form of academic leadership, though shaped by different research cultures and disciplines. It requires the supervisor to acquire and practise a high level of expert knowledge as well as transferable skills.⁸

Expert skills and academic competencies

The cornerstone of doctoral supervision is scientific expertise and expert knowledge within the field of study. This includes both subject matter expertise and discipline-specific research skills, such as proficiency in relevant methods, analysis and interpretation of results, as well as responsible research ethics, conduct and integrity. Notably, it is not necessary that the supervisor is working on the same research questions as the doctoral candidate. However, the research should be sufficiently related for the supervisor to fulfil the roles laid out above, as long as the specific expertise needed for the research of the doctoral candidate is provided by the co-supervisors or by other collaborators. While funding should be secured or guaranteed before the start of doctoral studies, supervisors should provide candidates with support in finding and applying for funding if needed.

Transferable skills and other competencies

However, expert skills and domain knowledge alone are not sufficient. The doctoral supervisor needs to have obtained a set of transferable skills and other competencies to be able to provide high-quality doctoral supervision. Core transferable skills and competencies include mentorship, communication skills, planning and management. Together, they underpin the capability of the doctoral supervisor to identify and adapt to different professional and educational needs of the doctoral candidate. A non-exhaustive overview of key transferable skills and competencies relevant to doctoral supervision is presented in Table 1.

The skills relevant to doctoral supervision are also relevant to many other parts of academic and non-academic work, and are applicable to many roles beyond that of a doctoral supervisor, e.g. teaching at other stages, mentoring of colleagues, or assuming management roles.

Supervision training and institutional responsibilities

The ability and responsibility to supervise is embedded in the profile of an academic. Therefore, such training in supervision must begin early in the academic career. It is an obligation of the institutions to provide training for doctoral supervisors, either by facilitating internally hosted workshops or by allocating financial resources for attending tailored training or coaching with specific application to doctoral education. Obtaining skills related to supervision must be easily accessible, encouraged and prioritised by the institutions, thus recognised as part of their professional development. Continuous discussion and refinement of these skills and competencies must be facilitated and prioritised by institutions, tailored to the relevant needs at

⁸ Eurodoc, "Transferable skills report", <https://eurodoc.net/skills-report-2018.pdf>

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each career stage.

Table 1: Examples of Transferable Skills and Competencies of Doctoral Supervisors

Mentorship and guidance	Communication and interpersonal relations	Planning and Management
<p>Providing constructive feedback to help the doctoral candidate improve</p> <p>Applying pedagogical and didactic skills to enhance the doctoral candidate's understanding and knowledge</p> <p>Offering a psychologically safe environment that encourages open sharing, where mistakes are treated as part of academic growth</p> <p>Fostering motivation and encouraging the doctoral candidate</p> <p>Facilitating academic discussions, promoting independence in scientific thought</p> <p>Fostering research ethics and integrity and promoting responsible scientific conduct</p>	<p>Maintaining open and clear communication, practicing active listening</p> <p>Being able to navigate and establish constructive routes for the resolution of conflicts or disagreements, utilising available resources where appropriate</p> <p>Fostering a healthy work-life balance among members of their academic environment</p> <p>Recognising the doctoral candidate's needs for further support (e.g. mental health), referring them to available resources as necessary</p> <p>Demonstrating cultural competences and avoiding potential misunderstandings or misinterpretations in communication</p>	<p>Practicing effective time management and allocating sufficient time for supervision</p> <p>Assisting the doctoral candidates in creating realistic plans and managing their time</p> <p>Setting achievable expectations and goals for research projects</p> <p>Helping the doctoral candidate in making well-founded decisions relating to their projects</p>

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Building inclusive and supportive academic environments

Academic culture needs to shift toward supporting a healthy work-life balance for doctoral candidates, as well as for everyone else working or studying within the sector. Such a culture supports the employment rights of doctoral candidates, promotes networking and interaction opportunities, encourages doctoral candidates to take vacations, and promotes reasonable working hours in line with their employment conditions. Such a culture also recognises the highly international and diverse environment of academia and proactively addresses cultural, language and accessibility barriers to minimise social isolation. By fostering an inclusive atmosphere, every individual can contribute according to their interests, abilities and preferences.

Academic institutions need to provide adequate support systems, such as an occupational health care provider or similar service, where doctoral candidates can turn to for mental health or other work environment-related issues. Academic institutions promote awareness of mental health issues among supervisors and offer them basic training in recognising mental health issues.

Supervisors play an important role in fostering a supportive research environment and being attentive to the well-being of doctoral candidates. This necessitates that they themselves receive adequate training on how to create a healthy work-life balance in a research environment and are able to support doctoral candidates in navigating the support systems provided by the institution.

For a broader view on mental health of early career researchers, including doctoral candidates, please refer to Eurodoc's previous statement "Towards Healthy Working Environments for Early Career Researchers".⁹

The academic environment

The doctoral candidate is part of an academic environment that can be composed of colleagues at the host institution, other institutions, non-academic organisations, as well as third-party organisations such as scientific societies, governmental organisations, or private stakeholders. As with doctoral education as a whole, supervision is fully embedded in the environment in which it takes place. The academic environment both supports and is co-created by the doctoral candidate and the supervisors. This means that there is a shared right and obligation for both the doctoral candidate and the supervisors to participate in and contribute to this environment, also in the form of representativity and participation to decision-making procedures.

While doctoral supervision is an individual relationship between one doctoral candidate and their supervision team, it stands in relation to the resources provided and created within the academic environment. The academic environment is a community ideally composed of peers

⁹ Eurodoc, "Towards healthy working environments for Early Career Researchers".
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13379273>

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of other doctoral candidates, and other academics from senior professors to undergraduate students. Together, this forms a research community for exchanging ideas and sharing experiences.

Doctoral supervision may extend beyond the primary supervisor to include additional participants who can provide supplementary support and resources. These individuals, often part of the broader academic or professional network surrounding the doctoral candidate, can contribute expertise and guidance that might otherwise fall solely to the supervisor. Such collaborative arrangements can be formalised through structured doctoral courses or group supervision sessions. While these collective resources play a vital role in enriching the doctoral experience, they are not intended to serve as a substitute for the essential, personalised engagement of individual supervision.

The candidate-supervision relationship is one with inherent hierarchy, vulnerability, and power imbalance. The academic environment provides an important opportunity for assessing doctoral supervision itself, providing feedback to the supervisor on their supervision. This can also help recognise cases where doctoral supervision is not working at an early stage. It is therefore important that the doctoral candidate is provided with sufficient information on institutional options to involve authorities outside of the relationship, if such involvement would become necessary.

Academic freedom

Both the doctoral candidate and their supervisors have the right to academic freedom. By setting out the mutual expectations at the beginning of doctoral education, guidance and autonomy is balanced and agreed upon. The interdependence of the candidate and the supervisors is acknowledged, and continuously realigned. Supervisors must find a balance between providing necessary guidance and allowing for sufficient autonomy for the candidate to develop independent research skills and critical thinking. The doctoral candidate is able to pursue research outside the field of the supervisor, under the condition that suitable, field-specific supervision can be obtained elsewhere and in reasonable agreement with the supervisor.

The PhD candidate has a right to a degree of academic freedom both as a research professional as well as a person enrolled in academic education. The doctoral candidate must acknowledge that their work inevitably involves the supervisor both scientifically and, in most countries, economically. This remains the case even when the doctoral candidate has, or develops, deeper expertise in a certain domain than their supervisors. Decision-making in the context of doctoral supervision always remains collaborative. In cases of disagreement - whether academic, ethical, or personal - mutual respect and open dialogue are essential. Institutions should provide support for resolving such conflicts when needed.

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Emerging trends and future challenges

Doctoral supervision faces a multitude of challenges, especially amid the digital transformation, requiring creative responses and proactive adaptation. With the advent of new technologies such as generative artificial intelligence, the traditional methods of conducting academic research are continuously reshaped. Both the candidate and supervisors can engage with these innovations thoughtfully, while being attentive to ethical implications and remaining critical of the integrity and authenticity of their scholarly work. Online tools facilitate the remote execution of a large portion of work, benefiting not only the doctoral candidate but also their supervisors. Both parties are encouraged to leverage these technologies, yet they should remain mindful of the importance of in-person exchanges and interactions for building an authentic and trust-based relationship. Additionally, broader societal shifts, such as those towards democratisation of knowledge, mental health awareness, and environmental sustainability are shaping how we work, learn, and interact. Overall, doctoral supervision will continue to evolve, preparing the next generation of early career researchers for an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

Conclusion

In essence, Eurodoc views doctoral supervision as an inherently challenging, but profoundly rewarding experience for both the doctoral candidate and their supervisors. Like the academic journey itself, the relationships between doctoral candidates and their supervisors are shaped by uncertainties, considerations, and discoveries that emerge over the course of the process of doctoral education. A healthy relationship is characterised by a continuous alignment of expectations that allows for dynamic adaptations in the education of the doctoral candidate. It is the institution's responsibility that supervisors receive the necessary support and resources to guide doctoral candidates effectively. By achieving this, we not only ensure a bright future for academia and science in Europe, but enrich the European society at large.

Ultimately, doctoral supervision is a mutual journey where the paths of the doctoral candidate and the supervisors converge, and after the conclusion of which they will diverge again. Throughout this journey, it is of paramount importance to uphold mutual respect for both the doctoral candidate's and supervisors' competences, research interests, and future plans. This shared experience not only fosters academic growth, but also lays the foundation for future collaborations, professional networks, and lasting intellectual contributions – and thus fundamentally shapes innovation and research in Europe.

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

